

Pharmacology :

Six of the final compounds were screened out for their effects on the central nervous system and their anti-inflammatory activity in mice. The approximate lethal doses in 50% of animals tested (ALD_{50})¹⁰ were also determined (Table 1). The compounds are relatively non-toxic except compound No. 5. All the compounds tested are CNS excitants at 1/5th of ALD_{50} . The anti-inflammatory activity¹¹ at 1/5th of ALD_{50} ranged between 8.4% to 43.6% protection of mice against carrageenin induced inflammation.

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Sterols of *Melitodes ornata**

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CONFIRMATION of spasmogenic activity in the ethanolic extract of the coral *Melitodes ornata*¹ (Family : Melitoides) prompted us to undertake its chemical investigation. The benzene soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract in which the activity was concentrated was chromatographed on

silica gel column. No pure compound was, however, obtained by this procedure. The benzene soluble fraction was, therefore, treated with alcoholic potassium hydroxide according to the method of Bergmann and Co-workers². The non-saponifiable fraction, so obtained, was chromatographed on silica gel column. Elution with benzene gave a fraction which on recrystallization from methanol gave a crystalline material(M), m.p. 130-32°, which, when examined on silica gel TLC plates impregnated with silver nitrate³; solvent system(1): chloroform: ethylacetate: acetic acid (97: 2. 3: 0.5 v/v) and solvent system (2): chloroform: hexane: acetic acid (25: 27: 0.5 v/v) and spraying reagent: 0.2% solution of dibromofluorescein in 96% ethanol exhibited four fluorescent spots under UV light, demonstrating thus the presence of four compounds in the crystalline material(M). The material(M) was then treated with acetic anhydride-pyridine to give a mixture of acetates which was resolved through the bromo derivatives to yield the following four compounds. Compound A ($C_{28}H_{46}O$) (M^+386), m.p., 145-46°, $[\alpha]_D - 64^\circ$ (chloroform); compound B ($C_{27}H_{46}O$) (M^+386), m.p. 140-42°, $[\alpha]_D - 39.2^\circ$ (chloroform); compound C ($C_{29}H_{50}O$) (M^+414), m.p. 136°, $[\alpha]_D - 35^\circ$ (chloroform) and compound D ($C_{29}H_{48}O$) (M^+400), m.p. 152-53°, $[\alpha]_D - 34.6^\circ$ (chloroform). The physical and chemical constants of compound A, compound B, compound C and compound D were very close to the sterols, brassicasterol⁴, cholesterol⁵, β -sitosterol⁷ and campesterol⁸ respectively. The identity was finally established by comparison (m.p. UV, IR, NMR, Mass and TLC) with the known data of the corresponding sterols.

The isolated sterols from the benzene soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract of *M. ornata* do not substantiate its spasmogenic activity.

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Compounds were synthesized according to following steps.

1. 2-methyl 6,7 or 8 benz. substituted 4-hydroxy quinolines were prepared by the previous reported method⁷.
2. 2-methyl 6,7 or 8 benz. substituted 4-chloro-quinolines were prepared by method reported in literature⁸.
3. Substituted amino acid ester hydrochlorides were prepared by reported method⁹.

Amoebicidal and Fungicidal Activity in New Quinolines

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Synthesis of 2-methyl 6,7 or 8 benz. substituted 4-amino substituted carboethoxy quinolines :

QUINOLINE compounds have an effective role in the therapy of microbial diseases. Its significance regarding amoebiasis is well established by the introduction of well known drugs like diidoquin, chloroquin etc.¹⁻³.

Substituted 4-chloro quinolines (0.01 moles) and amino acids ester hydrochloride (0.01 mole) were taken in ethoxy ethanol (15 ml) anhydrous K_2CO_3 (0.02 mole) was added to it and mixture was refluxed for 24 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and filtered. Ethoxy ethanol was removed under reduced pressure, the residue was mixed with water, made alkaline with NaOH solution and extracted with Et_2O , dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and ether was evaporated. The solid mass obtained was characterized by mps, analysis and I.R. and listed in Table 1.

The development of 8-hydroxy quinoline as a reputed clinically effective fungitoxic led to the recognition of quinoline group as antifungal agents³⁻⁴, extensive investigation has indicated that not only the 8-hydroxy quinoline but several derivatives of quinoline, which may or may not have 8-hydroxy substitution also possess good fungitoxic effects⁵⁻⁶.

The presence of characteristic bands of NH (3200 cm^{-1}), C=O(1680 cm^{-1}), C-O stretching of ester linkage (1340 cm^{-1} ; 1170 cm^{-1}) and C=N (1610 cm^{-1}) in the infra-red spectrum of 6-methoxy-2-methyl 4-(aminoethyl propionate) quinoline and characteristic bands of NH(3210 cm^{-1}) C=O (1685 cm^{-1}), C-O stretching of ester linkage (1250 cm^{-1} ; 1160 cm^{-1}) and C=N (1600 cm^{-1}) in

These observations prompted us to synthesize compounds with various amino acids incorporated in the quinoline nucleus at position 4 and thirteen of them tested for antimicrobial activity.

TABLE 1—6,7,8 BENZ. SUBSTITUTED 2-METHYL, 4-(AMINO SUBSTITUTED) CARBOETHOXY QUINOLINES

Compd. No.	X	R	Yield %	M.P. °C	Formula	N%		Amoebicidal activity at 1:1000 dilution against <i>S. russelli</i>
						Calcd.	Found	
1.	6-CH ₃	CHCH(CH ₃) ₂	40	76	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂	9.33	9.54	

* Part of Ph.D. Thesis of S. Ahmad.

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